

Digitalization in Marketing

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ABSTRACT

Aadyaa Originals Private Limited (“Aadyaa”) is a jewellery studio based in Pune, India which has a focus on handmade jewellery in metals like Sterling Silver, Brass and Copper. Established in 2013, Aadyaa has shipped more than 30,000 orders thus far within and outside India.

In this journey, Aadyaa has used Digital Marketing Media solely to cross milestones with regard to turnover, branding, presence in the market. Aadyaa started with a Facebook page wherein friends and family members were the first ones to like the page and become followers. With the increased interaction on Facebook page, Aadyaa launched its own website www.aadyaa.com to ensure a seamless shopping experience for its customers. While the website continues to be the only place where Aadyaa products can be bought online, the traffic to this website is still led by leaders in the digital marketing media like Facebook, Instagram and Google.

Based on a research paper published by Economic Times, online jewellery market in India is expected to reach a mark of INR 5300+ crores by 2020. This signifies a huge potential and to tap into the tier 2 and tier 3 markets, digital marketing media looks to be the most cost-effective marketing and branding channel. Digital marketing media can be used to create your audiences, target segments based on past data and get a boundary-less group of followers who are together only based on interest in a particular brand. All digital marketing media have evolved over a period of last 8 to 10 years and now offer a very powerful analytics dashboard to create your own ‘what-if’ scenarios. They also offer a plenty of datapoints gathered from publicly shared information of users over internet which help deciding in a budget.

Aadyaa has created varied marketing campaigns on these digital media during new collection launches, events, and exhibitions. As of now, Aadyaa boasts a fan following of over 400,000 on Facebook and close to 50,000 users on Instagram. This includes various celebrities in Indian Film Industry. Digital marketing media remains Aadyaa’s only channel for marketing and branding. Digital marketing contributes to over 75 percent of Aadyaa’s turnover now.

This paper delves deep into Aadyaa’s marketing strategy which has Digital Marketing as the strongest pillar. Paper has been presented in the form of a case study with the help of information provided by Mr. Jaydeep Hingne (Director – Aadyaa Originals Private Limited), research information available in various reports published, and analysis plus suitable assumptions of the author.

INTRODUCTION

As a definition, we can assume that “Digitalized Marketing” is the process wherein any medium or channel in the electronic form is used to connect or interact with customers for drawing their attention to provider’s services or products or make the brand presence felt.

Hence, any branding, marketing or advertising over media / channels such as television, internet, mobile devices, tablets, social platforms can be considered as a form of digitalized marketing. The interactions with customers over these channels could be one-way (provider to consumer) or two-way (provider to consumer and vice versa too).

The basic principles of marketing in print media have remained in-tact in digitalization era too. Good

creative design, clarity of the message, usage of language and words, localized themes have all maintained their stay in digitalized marketing.

Launch of Google search engine in 1998 could be considered as the start of evolution of digitalization in marketing. Although, digital billboards and hoardings were used in the industry even before that, those are the examples of static dynamic content without much of intelligence. Search engines like Alta Vista, WebCrawler, Yahoo existed before Google’s search engine, however, their operation was limited to only providing the references over web for the searched term. They never collected the data being searched nor really tried to implement a ranking mechanism for search results.

Google launched it’s one of the most successful products called ‘Ad-words’ in 2000 and it proved to be the game changer in the digital marketing arena. They followed it up with content marketing tools a few years after that. Around same time, in 2004, Mark Zuckerberg found Facebook in the US, the social giant, which connects with over a few billion people today across boundaries of nations. The idea behind Facebook was to introduce a tool for people to peep into other people’s lives and share their own stories.

Over a period of time, all the tools and concepts such as SEO (Search Engine Optimization), SEM (Search Engine Marketing), business analytics, traceability of users’ path on internet, users’ acceptance to share

their certain personal information over internet have evolved dramatically and have helped in the meaningful spends in the digitalized marketing field.

When Aadyaa launched its operations in 2013, it started with a Facebook business page wherein post can be created, photos can be shared and information about the products, services and about the brand can be displayed. Soon after, its Facebook page (www.facebook.com/aadyaaoriginals) gathered momentum and started going viral.

Team Aadyaa then decided to make use of marketing offered by Facebook on the business page and started creating various marketing campaigns. These campaigns led to increased revenue, increased number of followers across the globe, and a platform to interact with its customers. Later on, Aadyaa spread its marketing portfolio in other digital marketing channels such as Instagram, Google products, and Twitter.

As of 15th September 2018, Aadyaa’s fanbase on Facebook has crossed the milestone 400,000 people. On Instagram, its inching towards 50,000 mark.

A quick snapshot of Aadyaa’s Facebook page followers for last 2 years is given below. Growth is 2.7x in last 2 years which could not have been achieved in traditional marketing media.

Print Media vs Digital Media

One of the most debated questions in the field of marketing today is whether print or digital media is more effective. There is no clear answer to this question, especially considering the Indian user base. While tier 1, 2 and even tier 3 cities have become digital savvy today, there exists a huge population which is far away from any sort of Digital media in India.

Government of India has undertaken ambitious programs such as Digital India under which a huge

number of services have been made available to Indian citizens and awareness is also created to help people.

As per Magna report published on livemint.com, total spend of advertising in India is expected to hit INR 68,000 crores in 2018. Digital is expected to pick a staggering pie of almost 40% in this huge budget. As per the report, India is probably the only market in the world, where print media also showing growth irrespective of the hurdles like demonetization and GST rollouts.

Summary of Digital vs Print media is as below:

Digital Media	Print Media
More engaging with users	Static content, hence less engaging with users
Spending amount can be decided and altered during campaigns	Spend amount is pre-decided and cannot really be altered
Return on Investment (ROI) measure is relatively easier compared to print media	ROI measurement is difficult in print
Audience can be chosen based on the product / service in contention	Audience cannot be chosen or filtered as such.
Content of most marketing campaigns can be tailored within micro groups of users	Same content goes to all sets of users
Campaigns can go viral	Spread of print media campaigns is at relatively fixed place
Needs internet for most digital media to operate the marketing campaigns	Does not need any internet connectivity as such. Only distribution network of newspapers, magazines is required

In light of the above, Aadyaa has chosen to spend its monies only on digital media for marketing and stayed away from print media. This approach has yielded very good results to Aadyaa and they have managed to achieve approximately 10x returns on the spends done in their digital marketing.

Aadyaa witnessed digital media’s power when Bollywood celebrities like Vidya Balan, Shraddha Kapoor wore and flaunted Aadyaa’s creations. Apart from Bollywood, celebrities from other industries, such as Sonali Kulkarni, Spruha Joshi, Parna Pethe, Mithila Palkar, Anumol have adorned Aadyaa’s creations and their posts have helped Aadyaa garner immense popularity and increased revenue in a very short while.

Portfolio within Digital Media

As far as portfolio of Digital media in marketing is considered, following key types can be considered. While this list is not exhaustive as such, and various other types also can be added to it, key types have been picked to demonstrate the expanse of digital marketing media.

Out of all these types, Aadyaa has chosen only social, internet ads and SEO/SEM related marketing spends till now. Return on investment achieved in these media is well above the industry benchmarks (2x to 4x revenue compared to spends) set by internet giants like Google and Facebook.

Aadyaa will continue to focus on these digital media to reach out to its existing customers as well as mine new customers based on their preferences about jewellery.

Insights from Digital Marketing

A vast amount of data gets captured when any of the campaign is run through digital marketing medium. Through this data, important insights can be gathered and can be made to ensure better utilization of marketing budgets for the organization.

At Aadyaa, following insights are always being watched closely for their campaigns:

1. How many users have connected through the campaign
2. How many conversions have happened through the spend of a particular campaign

3. What is the cost at which conversions are taking place
4. How many concurrent users are connecting to portal of www.aadyaa.com through the marketing campaigns
5. Where are the users based? City and country
6. How users are connecting to the campaigns – desktops/laptops, mobiles, apps, tablets
7. Is there any particular pattern in the buyers' age group / gender / ethnicity?

Limitations of Digitalized Marketing

While digital media are a boon for advertisers as they assist in better utilization of their marketing budgets, from a user's perspective, it may just become an overdose too soon. A typical user having a smart phone in hand and having access to Internet, will get continuous promotional notifications on his social media accounts, internet browsers, search engines.

At the moment, users are enjoying their social accounts free of cost only because there are promotional campaigns run by advertisers. There will soon be a time when users will get an option to pay a fee to get access to use their social accounts without

any ads as such. For the social account provider, it will still be making a huge profit, but for advertisers, it will be a lost potential customer.

Hence, it is essential for the marketing community to create the campaigns cautiously so that only carefully selected audience with high probability of conversion gets targeted and it doesn't act like a bombardment for other set of users.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can see that there is a huge scope for digitalized marketing in India. While Aadyaa has tried to explore digital marketing's potential in jewellery sector, other key sectors such as banking and financial services, manufacturing, real estate, logistics, textile, electronics also can be targeted well with rightfully created campaigns.

With most advanced tools and techniques in analytics, SEO, SEM, targeting a right user is now a reality. This can help in achieving new customers as well as

maximizing the potential of existing set of customers as well.

While the number of brands keep growing every day, it is of paramount importance to create your own space with rightful marketing and branding with the help of media that supports your organization's products and services the most.

Citations and references

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3. <https://www.facebook.com/aadyaaoriginals>
4. <https://www.instagram.com/aadyaaoriginals>
5. <http://www.aadyaa.com>

About the Author: Dr Satish Marathe

Dr Marathe has been working in the field of education for last 36 years. He has worked as a Registrar and Visiting Faculty in several institutes in Pune and Mumbai. He is currently working as Associate Professor in Tilak Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune. He also has a keen interest in teaching with focus on Micro and Macro Economics.

Dr Marathe has also worked as a trainer and have been a part of Humanist Movement. He believes in continuous learning process and one shouldn't stop learning at all. He has received PhD in Management in July 2016 from Tilak Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune. Before his PhD, he has completed his MDBA (Marketing) from IMDR, BSc (Statistics) from Shivaji University, and M.A. (Economics) from Pune University.

Portfolio:

- Tilak Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune (June 2017 till date):
 - Teaching in Management Department to BBA and MBA Program.
 - Teaching in Commerce Department to B.com and M.com Program.
- N.L. Dalmia Institute of Management (2015 to 2016) || NMITD Mumbai (2011 to 2014) || Institute of Management Development and Research (1980 to 1995 & 2008 to 2011)
 - Faculty for communication, general management and organization behavior subjects
 - Registrar with General Administration Duties: Admission, Scheduling, Timetables
 - Student Management: Supervising all the administrative arrangements for all the events, festivals, competitions etc. conducted on campus
 - Examination: Supervising examination related all activities (From Form submission to Result declaration and arranging convocation)
 - Accounts: Purchasing material for educational institute, Supervising Payrolls
 - HR: Recruitment, Training and Development, Employee Performance appraisal
 - Supervising Housekeeping and Maintenance work at the institute

- Institute for studies in Technology (1995 to 2008)
 - Faculty for Organization behavior, PPM, Economics, Marketing, Case studies
 - Placements and internships for students.
- Corporate Trainer
 - Trained employees of Bank of Bhutan in Customer Relationship Management
 - Training program on Personality development, English Improvement and Public speaking for employees of R&D group
- Visiting Faculty for subjects such as Marketing, Business Statistics, Managerial economics, Market Research, Communication and leadership skills, industrial organizations and methods:
 - Symbiosis Institute of Management Services, Pune, India.
 - Institute for Studies in Technology and Engineering, Pune, India.
 - Tilak Maharashtra Vidyapeeth, Pune, India.
 - Arihant Management Institute, Pune, India.
 - Sunrise Training Centre, Pune, India.
 - Sudarshan Management Institute, Pune, India.
 - Technical Institute, Pune, India.
 - Institute of Management and Career Courses, Pune, India.
 - Mitcon institute of Management, Balewadi, Pune, India.
- Presented opinions on live television show:
 - Modern Management Methods on 28th January 2013
 - Union Budget 2013 on 13th March 2013
- Research Papers published in journals:

Sr#	Title with Page No	Journal	ISSN/ISBN No
1	Management Education', page 168 to 172	ROYAL	ISSN-2218-8158
2	"On line shopping", page 42 to 46	ROYAL	ISSN-2218-8158
3	"A CRITICAL Analysis of Consumer expectations from online purchasing	Mahratta	ISSN-0076-2571
4	Automation and Employability	NA	--